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Review Article

A Review Article on Exploring Forensic Mental Health Nursing Ethics and Practice - Roles, Loyalties and Photo documentation Practices

Karthikeswari*

Government Institute of Medical Science, College of Nursing, Uttar Pradesh, India

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ABSTRACT

Forensic nursing, formally recognized by the ANA is a relatively young nursing specialty. Although ethical concerns and dilemmas abound there remains a paucity of published research studies on the ethical dimensions guiding forensic nursing practice. In addition, there is a lack of educational resources related to ethics from sources such as the forensic nursing society's professional organization, academic texts, and journals. Yet, forensic nursing practice occurs in an environment where providers are at substantial risk for role confusion and role conflict. Forensic nurses may also experience conflicts of interests or conflicting interests. They encounter ethical dilemmas that may create moral distress and have extremely limited resources for guidance. Forensic nursing is a specialty practice that encounters situations involving sexual assault, child abuse, homicide, torture, and other tragedies that are emotionally charged and involve medico-legal implications. The outcomes associated with these events may have life-long negative effects for the patient, their families and loved ones, their community as well as for the accused, suspects and perpetrators of the violence and his/her family and loved ones.

INTRODUCTION

Issues related to clinical, professional, and organizational ethics within forensic nursing practice span the realms of clinical practice, research, education, administration, and policy. Forensic nurses find themselves at the intersection of healthcare and the law, yet there remains an absence of forensic nursing research on topics such as dual loyalty to the patient and society; to

nursing and the criminal justice system), professional values (e.g., value development, response to conflicting values), and ethical decision making processes. There is also a lack of published articles addressing conflicts of interest and conflicting interests, and where the two concepts overlap, in clinical forensic nursing practice² Interestingly, within the Scopes and Standards of Forensic Nursing Practice (2009),

***Corresponding Author:** Karthikeswari

Address: Government Institute of Medical Science, College of Nursing, Uttar Pradesh, India

Email ✉: vkarthikha@gmail.com

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there are several references to the ethical paradigms of forensic nursing practice although a literature search for such a paradigm or their application to practice was unsuccessful within the forensic nursing literature and textbooks. Discourse surrounding forensic medical services for unconscious patients serves as an exemplar of the concerns described above³

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To collaborate with others in the future who wish to do the same for the populations they serve.
2. To serving as a change agent and understand the risks associated with raising head above the crowd and objectively speaking out about emotionally charged and controversial subjects
3. To Speaking up for those whose voices are not valued, or whose voices are actively silenced carries risk⁴

LEGAL ASPECTS:

- Indian penal code.
- Criminal procedure code.
- Indian evidence act.
- Protection of women from domestic violence act (pwdva), 2005.
- The protection of children from sexual offences act ,2012.(pocso)
- Criminal law amendment act 2013 on sexual offences.(claa)
- Sexual harassment of women at workplace (prevention, prohibition & redressal) act 2013.
- Guidelines and protocols , medicolegal care for survivors/victims of seual violence issued by MOHFW⁵

FORMS OF SEXUAL VIOLENCE INCLUDE:

- Coerced / forced sex in marriage or live-in relationships or dating relationships
- Rape by strangers.
- Systematic rape during armed conflict, sexual slavery.

- Unwanted sexual advances or sexual harassment.
- Sexual abuse of children.
- Sexual abuse of people with mental and physical disabilities.
- Forced prostitution and trafficking for the purpose of sexual exploitation
- Child and forced marriage.
- Denial of the right to use contraception or to adopt other measures to protect against STIs⁶
- Forced abortion and forced sterilisation.
- Female genital mutilation
- Inspections for virginity.
- Forced exposure to pornography.
- Forcibly disrobing and parading naked any person.

Section 164A CrPC lays out following legal obligations of the health care workers in cases of sexual violence:

- Examination of cases of rape shall be conducted by RMP either government or private hospital.
- Examination without delay
- Record consent
- Exact time of start and close of examination
- Report without delay to IO/ Magistrate.

CLAA 2013, 357C CrPC:

- Both private and public health professionals are obligatedd for treatment.
- Denial - punishable under 166B IPC - imprisonment 1year or fine or both⁴
- 222 IPC ; identity of rape victims are never disclosed.
- 114A IEA - presumption of absence of consent.

ROLE OF DOCTOR UNDER POC SO ACT:

1. No hospital under the jurisdiction of the indian constitution can refuse to admit the victim of child sexual abuse for examination and treatment ever. This issue has been reemphasized in Section 23of the-criminal Law Amendment ACT 357C CrPC.

2. No doctor or health care professional should demand from the child abuse victim, any legal records or force them to comply with any legal procedure or to provide any documentation before initiating the treatment or examination⁷ Legal procedures can be done later, even FIR can be lodged after initiating required medical care. Providing immediate medical care to the victim should be the utmost priority.
3. It is now mandatory for the doctors to register a medico legal case in all incidents of child sexual abuse. Failure of mandatory rejection could result in Six months imprisonment and/or a fine under section 21 of the POCSO Act, 2012
4. All hospitals in India, whether government run or private, have to provide first-aid or immediate medical treatment, free of cost, to the victims⁸ of all kind of sexual offences(child sexual abuse victims included in this provision).(Section 166A CrPC, 357C CrPC)
5. It is mandatory that the medical examination must be conducted by only a Registered Medical Practitioner at a government hospital or a hospital run by a local authority or any private hospital, within 24 hours from the time of receiving information about an offence In case the victim is a girl child, the medical examination shall be conducted by a woman doctor.
6. The medical examination shall be conducted in the presence of the parent of the child or any other person in whom the child reposes trust or confidence .
7. In cases, where the parent of the child or other person referred in sub section cannot be present, for any reason, during the medical examination of the child, the medical examination shall be conducted in the presence of a woman nominated by the head of the medical institution⁹
8. Medical examination will be conducted at the hospital by two people- one, to collect evidence and another to document injuries ,markings, bruises etc...roles for the doctor include therapeutic role(medical examination for treatment),medicolegal examination⁶ and another to collect evidence for forensic tests¹⁰

DISCUSSION

During discussions of potential ethical conflicts, many forensic nurses become focused solely on the pelvic exam, specifically, the insertion of a speculum into the vagina of an unconscious female patient. Considerations are not given to other related invasive procedures (e.g., sample collection from anal or oral cavities), equivalent concerns for male or transgender patients, nor grounds for suspicion of assault itself.

Individual decisions and even program policies have been based on what the forensic nurse would want if s/he were the patient or based on an assumed fear on the part of the forensic nurse of risking his/her professional nursing license(s). These decision processes are not consistently evidence-based nor patient centered and represent a weak ethical decision making process

Much of the formal and informal discourse appeared to be anecdotal at best and similar to the exemplar shared above. These conversations tended to focus primarily on female patients and their genitalia. Yet there was a lack of evidence-based or research-informed literature related to the use of digital imaging for photo documentation among forensic nurses. The same held true for forensic nurses concerns.

CONCLUSION

A second exemplar, and the impetus behind the data generating section of my doctoral studies, involves the practice and policy surrounding photo documentation, particularly digital photo documentation. Concerns around the use of digital imaging technology for photo documentation emerged through formal and informal discussions

during an International Association of Forensic Nurses symposium on photo documentation, posts on general and sub-specialty discussion boards, articles exploring the use and purpose of digital imaging technology, and questions posed during forensic nurse training and presentations.

involving the practice of photo documentation and use of digital imaging technology. This gap in the literature included both extra-genital and ano-genital photo documentation practices. To develop best practices, policy statements or guidelines, and to address ethical concerns surrounding the use of digital imaging technology in clinical forensic nursing practice, it is critical to move beyond anecdotal accounts.

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CONCLUSION

Herbal plant extract and their oils were found to have antibacterial activity. Easy availability of plants and their effectiveness helps manufacturers with cause effective benefits with less side-effects, various ongoing studies and the diverse properties of herbs, serves as a guide for the discovery of new antibacterial agents. The current knowledge regarding antibacterial from plant provide strong recommendation for future research. Plants represent living chemical factories for the biosynthesis of tremendous range of secondary metabolites that constitute the foundation for herbal medicines prepared from medicinal plants. Compounds of natural origin exhibiting biological activity always attracted the attention of scientists involved in infectious disease caused by bacterial pathogens.

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